

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

CONCRETIZATION OF THE METHODOLOGICAL STRUCTURE OF THE LESSON IN TERMS OF THE PROPORTION OF STUDENTS' ANALYTICAL AND HEURISTIC ACTIVITIES IN TRAINING PRACTICE

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Abstract

In the article in scientific sources (researched by us), attention is drawn to the existence of diversity of opinions in the interpretations of the concept of the form of organization of training and it is stated that the main form of organization of training and education work in general education schools is confirmed by training practice. It is also shown that the efficiency of managing the learning process, which is a complete system, depends on finding the right balance between its content and form.

It is emphasized in the research work that the nature of the methodological substructure of the lesson does not depend only on the content of its general didactic structure. The didactic structure reflects the main stages of training and the organization of a modern lesson. The connecting links between didactic and methodical structures serve the internal logical-psychological substructures of the lesson. The internal infrastructure of the lesson consists of elements that reflect the teaching-cognitive process.

It is shown in the work that teachers with prior experience comprehensively analyze the educational material for all components, as well as from the logical, psychological, educational and didactic aspects, and based on this, determine the ratio of analytical and heuristic types in the student's activity. The methodological structure of management is determined on this basis.

Keywords: the structure of the lesson; didactic structure; methodological structure; analytical and heuristic activity; internal infrastructure; logical-psychological infrastructure.

Relevance of the research topic. It is clear both from the research of the scientific source and from the pedagogical experience that the continuous improvement of the lesson as the main organizational form of education is an urgent and permanent problem. In our modern times, the learning process, which is perceived as a way to implement education according to the 4th industrial revolution, should be student-centered (learner-centered). In order to realize this requirement, the optimal relations of analytical and heuristic activity of the student should be adjusted along with other conditions in the training process. The existence of such an environment in the training process depends on the logical connection of substructures (external and internal structures) of its organizational form, the selection of elements of each substructure and the level of realization of the functions of these elements. Despite what has been said, we claim that "Specification of the methodological structure of the lesson in terms of the ratio of students' analytical and heuristic activities in educational practice" and the formation of a student-centered (educational-centered) learning process, which is perceived as a way of implementing education in accordance with the associations of the IV industrial revolution, is an actual research issue aiming at solving the problem.

Methodological basis of the study. In the process of conducting research, L. Bertalanfi's "System analysis idea" [9; 8] was used as an important branch of dialectics and rose to the level of its alternative, "System-

structural approach", empirical-theoretical and theoretical methods of scientific cognition, internal relations of the forms of scientific cognition, and various pedagogical and psychological research generalizations were used as a methodological basis.

Interpretation of research materials. In scientific sources (researched by us), there is a diversity of opinions in the interpretations of the concept of the form of training organization. However, there is no one against considering the form of organization of training as a component of this process. According to our subjective understanding, it is necessary to understand "the organizational form of training (the way of implementation of the development and change process-education) as the mode of existence of its content, its own internal organization, structure that makes it possible for the content to exist." The effectiveness of managing the learning process, which is a complete system, depends on finding the right balance between its content and form.

Training practice has confirmed that the main organizational form of training and education work in general education schools is the lesson.[6;324]. Different authors put forward interesting ideas about the lesson. For example, according to M.I. Makhmutov, the lesson is the main movement form of training, which provides the content, principles and methods of training, is planned and regulated by the teacher within a certain time frame, and appears as a set of teacher-student relations. [13; 427-431]. MNSkatkin noted that "the lesson is a finished part or cell of the pedagogical

process to one degree or another." [16; 149]. B.A.Ahmadov wrote: "The teacher directs the collective cognitive activity (and the process of forming the correct attitude to life) of a group of students with a fixed composition for the school year according to a specific regime (and taking into account the individual characteristics of each member of the collective)" [3; 188]. A.O.Mehrabov, an academician of the Russian Academy of Education, wrote similar to the opinion of Prof. B.A.Bashirov that the lesson is used as one of the important concepts of modern pedagogy. It still holds its force as a pedagogical requirement under the guidance of the teacher, according to the schedule, with the determined contingent of students, within the time frame. They are fulfilled as the parameters of the standard lesson.[8; 18]

The lesson, which is considered the main organizational form of training, has a long history. Professor A.N.Abbasov writes that in the history of the school's development, there have been various training systems. In those systems, separate forms of organization: individual-group form of training (in medieval schools), mutual training form (Bell-Lancaster system in England), individualized training form according to the abilities of students (Manheim), brigade-laboratory form (A modified form of Dalton's plan, applied in Soviet schools in the 20s of the 20th century) is reserved for the class-lesson form (which has been in development for more than 350 years). Purpose of education, content and methods are manifested in the conditions of interaction in its organizational form. The emergence, development, improvement and gradual disappearance of some of the various forms of training organization were related to the demands and needs of the developing society.[1; 286]

B.A.Ahmadov and A.Q.Rzayev wrote in this regard: "It is known that it was Yakomensky who theoretically justified the class-lesson system. I.F.Herbert developed such a unified (standard) scheme of the lesson: explanation of new material ("clarity stage"), creation of a connection between new knowledge and old knowledge ("association stage"), summarization of knowledge ("systemization stage") and studies ("method stage"). A. Disterweg demanded to prioritize the development of thinking in the lesson, and K.D.Ushinsky demanded to combine the development of the student's personality with imparting knowledge in the lesson. Thus, the lesson has passed a certain stage of development throughout history and was able to prove itself after all kinds of tests." [3; 189]

The call for the democratization of education defined in the Education Reform Program in Azerbaijan inevitably requires a revision of the concept of lessons, thinking in the direction of determining its modern version that obeys humanistic and democratic principles, and the preparation of concrete proposals [11; 18]. Improving the management of the educational process depends to a great extent on the interpretation of the theoretical and practical foundations of its system of organizational forms, didactic connections and dependencies with other educational components of this system. Since the lesson is the main organizational

form of education, it is an urgent requirement to continuously improve it [7; 249].

Improving the lesson (due to its basic form) is an urgent requirement. In fairness, it can be said that a lot of research has been done on improving the lesson, and this process is currently ongoing; its types and structure are being clarified, the theory and practice of organizing and managing the learning material at a level that can play the role of a form of procedural movement is being developed. Despite these, there is no unanimity in solving the issues related to the lesson even now. Sometimes we also come across attempts to equate didactic concepts with some kind of mental concepts in defining the types and types of lessons [5; 547].

The form of their existence (the teaching material and methods for the lesson together appear in the place of content) cannot fail to improve in connection with the improvement of the educational material that contains a part of the human social experience and the educational methods aimed at its mastery (such is the dialectic of the categories "Form" and "Content!"). Psychologists have done a lot of work on improving the lesson. It is not accidental that along with "traditional lesson" there are also "modern lesson", "developmental lesson", "problematic lesson", "staged lesson", "synthetic lesson", etc. concepts reflecting quality signs are used.

It should be noted that the modern lesson and the requirements for it were formed through intense pedagogical, psychological, and methodological research. It is true that the use of the term "modern lesson" is ambiguous in the pedagogical literature. They consider it more appropriate to talk about the changes in the requirements for the lesson, its construction in accordance with the school's current tasks and the use of appropriate terminology.

"Two stages can be conventionally distinguished in the development of new pedagogical thinking. In the first stage, during the scientific-critical analysis of the traditional didactic system, the optimization of the lesson was of special importance as the main psychological and pedagogical problem. As an alternative to the traditional lesson, the meaning of the modern lesson was born at this stage" the author of the opinion is prof. A.A.Alizadeh wrote that the word "modern" in the meaning of "modern lesson" has its own heuristic meaning. "Modern lesson" does not mean "today's lesson". A lesson based on the successes of the time is called a modern lesson. In this sense, they usually distinguish two aspects that are organically connected with each other. Often, when they say modern lesson, they understand it only as raising the scientific-theoretical level of the lesson, modernizing it. The lesson should reflect the achievements of the time according to its scientific and theoretical level. This is indisputable. However, it would be one-sided to explain the meaning of modern lessons only in this root. We are talking about a pedagogical phenomenon. The word "modern" also characterizes the lesson. The lesson becomes modern not only due to its scientific-theoretical level, but also due to its pedagogical concept - it is built with new dimensions of pedagogical thinking. Modern

knowledge with modern methods - modern teaching can be generally characterized as follows. [2;17-18]

It should be admitted that as a form of organization of training, it is still being effectively researched, its types and structure are being clarified, the theory and practice of organization and management of the training material at the level that can play the role of the form of its procedural movement is being worked out. But despite this, there is no unanimity in solving the issues related to the lesson (characterizing it as a whole system). For example, the classification of the lesson has long been one of the topics of didactics discussion.

Many didactic (as well as methodical) studies have been conducted on the issue of lesson typology. The authors conducting research in this direction have taken this or that sign or aspect of the lesson as the main one during the classification. Y.A.Talibov, A.A. Agayev, I.N. Isayev, A.I. Eminov's "Pedagogy" book, authored by them, states: "On the issue of lesson types and structure, a group of authors based the training process on: a) introductory lessons; b) first familiarization lessons with educational material; c) classes that create understanding, etc. The second group of authors considers the classes as the main teaching methods: a) lecture classes; b) interview classes; c) laboratory exercises are divided into classes, etc. The third group of authors classify the lessons in relation to the didactic tasks in front of him [11; 159-160].

By the way, let's also emphasize that in modern lesson theory and teaching practice, the division of lessons according to didactic goals is used as a work tool, and at the same time, they make such a correction that "purely" (which only provides new information, or only knowledge, skills and habit-building) lessons are rarely encountered, as are pure programming and pure problem-based lessons. In the real teaching process, almost every lesson fulfills a set of didactic goals, and at this time, various teaching methods are used. It should be noted that the idea of the typology of the lesson according to the purpose is connected with the name of B.P.Yesipov. He distinguished 6 types of lessons. See: [12; 34]. The typology presented by B.P.Yesipov was presented by Azerbaijani pedagogues-academic M.M.Mehdzade and prof. N.M.Kazimov did not deny either [6; 329]. N.M.Kazimov wrote that this division has advantages. First of all, the same style is expected in the naming of lesson types, and secondly, the division is based on the solution of didactic tasks. However, this division also has its shortcomings. First of all, during real training, for example, there is no lesson that only acquires new knowledge, or only a lesson that forms skills and habits. Several didactic tasks can be performed in a lesson of this or that type. Second, the types of lessons do not properly correspond to the stages of learning. This division does not take into account, for example, the type of lesson corresponding to the first stage of training - understanding the teaching material.[4; 173]

Our attention has always been drawn by M.I.Makhmutov's reasoning and it is still drawing more attention today. M.I.Makhmutov stated the goals of organizing the workshop (taking into account the princi-

ple of difficulty): a) learning new material; b) improvement of knowledge, skills and habits; c) classified based on the combination of three goals such as control and assessment of the learning rate [15;76]. He showed that "a modern lesson differs from a traditional lesson in its goals, content, organizational-methodical aspects, degree of activity of students' activities, structure, pace, characteristics of TV, etc. differs with Despite their diversity, modern lessons (based on the principle of problematic) can be combined into two groups: a) problematic lessons; b) non-problematic lessons. The difference between them should be found in the methods and means of training and the structure of the lesson. It is possible to distinguish the logical-psychological (internal) and didactic (external) structure of problematic lessons. From the point of view of internal structure, the lesson is considered problematic when the teacher deliberately creates a problematic situation and organizes the search activity of students to pose a problem and search for and perform independent learning (high degree of problematic) or poses a problem and solves it himself, shows the logic of the idea on the search situation to the students. A high level of students' cognitive activity is achieved when students' cognitive, interest and emotional feelings are reconciled with the problematic situation. [15; 77-78]

Here we see some new elements of the modern lesson view. The didactic indicator of a problematic lesson is its complexity, "syntheticity". This is not the same as a combined lesson. In a synthetic lesson, several didactic issues are solved at the same time (this is also the case in a combined lesson). But this is not the main thing. The essence of the synthetic lesson is that, as a rule, the repetition of what has been passed is combined with access to new material, the learning of new things begins at the stage of actualization of necessary knowledge, the acquisition of new things is connected with independent work, knowledge is systematically applied to practice, the repetition of knowledge, skills and habits is a new connection and is realized continuously in reconciliations. The complexity of the main stages (explanation of new material, its comprehension, assimilation of new concepts, development of habits, etc.) is observed as the main feature of a problematic lesson. From a didactic point of view, a non-problematic lesson differs from a problematic one by the exact separation of the stages of the learning process, and there is no synthesis of the main elements of the lesson. [10; 416]

The structure of the lesson cannot be established without taking into account the didactic goals, the content of the educational material, as well as the general methods of education. Actualization, the formation of new concepts and methods of action and the application of the acquired ones act as the results of the learning process, and they are solved in one lesson as three generalized didactic tasks of the lesson, at different levels, regardless of its type. They are also components of the general didactic structure of the lesson (at the same time, they are the main stages of the lesson). The general didactic structure of the lesson is the algorithm of the lesson organization, the general instruction. This structure is opened and concreted in the methodical

structure of the lesson. Its elements are different types of activities of the teacher and the student. If the number of components of the didactic structure is constant, the number of elements of the methodical structure is a variable quantity. This determines many variants of the methodical structure of the lesson. It is practically impossible to provide a uniform methodological structure for all subjects, all types and types of lessons. This structure can only be imagined in the form of a model [14;102-104].

The bases of the substructures differ from each other: the didactic structure is built on the basis of the system of didactic tasks and the logic of the learning process; a methodical structure is established based on the didactic structure; the internal substructure of mastering is built on the logic of the student's productive mental activity. The difference between the structures of a problematic lesson and a non-problematic lesson is that the logical-psychological structure of a problematic type of lesson is determined by both the general logic of the mastering process and the logic of creative mental activity. [418-419]

The nature of the methodological substructure of the lesson does not depend only on the content of its general didactic structure. The didactic structure reflects the main stages of training and modern lessons. The links between the didactic and methodical structures serve the internal logical-psychological substructures of the lesson. The internal infrastructure of the lesson consists of elements that reflect the teaching-cognitive process.

The internal substructure of the lesson consists of such relationships of elements that reflect the teaching-cognitive process, where the teaching-cognitive process of recovery of acquired knowledge and experience and the process of assimilation of new ones begins with feelings and perceptions, and then new knowledge is produced, understood, understood through logical operations. Generalization of separate properties and signs allows to systematize what has been learned. This process ends with the inclusion of new knowledge in the system of old knowledge (acquired). In this process, usually the elements of the teaching-cognitive process are not directly visible, they are not felt, they are expressed in the following elements of the methodical substructure: recovery-inquiry, studies, etc.; correctness of understanding-answers, questioning, judgment and logical conclusions, rules of application, etc.; generalization - in being able to connect parts of knowledge, in the correctness of determining the location of the new in the previously mastered, etc.

The functional connection of these elements and their sequence determine the general logic of appropriation. They are directly related to the reproductive and productive activities of students. The creative nature of learning is directly related to the logic of the productive mental process (setting and solving the learning problem). Therefore, one more substructure should be taken into account in the management of the training process related to creative search activity. Therefore, the nature and types of the student's and teacher's activities should be taken into account when solving the issue of recon-

ciliation of the methodical structure of the main organizational form of the training process with its internal substructures. Although the methodical structure aimed at the student's analytical activity is related to the methodical structure aimed at his creative search activity, they are not identical. Thus, if the student's learning activity is analytical, the methodical structure corresponds to the general logic of the mastering process, and if it is heuristic, the logic of the student's productive mental activity should also be taken into account.

The methodical structure of the lesson is determined by the didactic structure, education, training and development tasks, as well as the type of activity of the teacher and student. The optimality of the structure of the lesson mainly depends on the consideration and determination of the following factors: a) the content of the training material; b) didactic goals and didactic tasks; c) training methods and means; ç) age and individual characteristics of students; e) level of students' ability to learn.

When determining the methodical structure of the lesson and choosing the appropriate option, the unique professionalism, mastery, and preparation of the teacher is an important condition.

Teachers with advanced experience comprehensively analyze the learning material for all components, as well as from the logical, psychological, educational and didactic aspects, and based on this, determine the ratio of analytical and heuristic types in the student's activity. The methodological structure of management is determined on this basis.

Teachers with advanced experience analyze the learning material for all components, as well as from the logical, psychological, educational and didactic aspects, and based on this, determine the ratio of analytical and heuristic types in the student's activity. The methodological structure of management is determined on this basis. This can be seen in the fragments of the following sample lesson that we observed in the schools of the districts covered in the North-West zone of Azerbaijan.

In the lesson conducted by Elmira Gurbanova, a high-category mathematics teacher of Katex village secondary school in Balakan region, on the topic of "Pythagorean theorem", the optimal ratio of analytical and heuristic activities of students was determined based on a rigorous analysis, so we witnessed that each of the students acted as a participant in the determination of regularity, which was perceived as the goal of this topic.

It should be noted that the lesson began with studying the results of homework. It soon became clear that everyone got the same result during the homework: the sum of the areas of the squares on the legs is equal to the area of the square on the hypotenuse.

The teacher E. Gurbanova posed the following question to the students: "Are the areas of the squares built on the two smaller sides of all triangles equal to the area of the square built on the third side, or is this true only for right-angled triangles?"

Students were suggested to consider this situation as well.

Without wasting too much time, it was determined that the areas of the squares built on two sides of a non-right triangle are in no way equal to the area of the square built on the third side.

As a result of the practical work, such a rule was formulated (option I): In a right-angled triangle, the areas of the squares built on the legs are equal to the area of the square built on the hypotenuse.

Continuing the lesson process, the teacher was able to formulate the law in the following way by con-

ducting an appropriate interview with the students (option II): The sum of the squares of the lengths of the legs of a right-angled triangle is equal to the square of the length of the hypotenuse. E. Gurbanova has created an environment where their analytical and heuristic activities take place in a different proportion than before, by offering students to justify the truth of this regularity. He directed the students' attention to the drawing in the form of Figure-1 in order to guide the search process with high cognitive activity and stated that

Figure 1

Let's find and sum a^2 and b^2 see if it works or not. Students know the concept of cosine of an angle: in a right triangle, the ratio of the leg adjacent to the angle to the hypotenuse is the cosine of that angle. Students see the $\cos\alpha = \frac{c_b}{c}$ relationship without difficulty, but this dependence and its corresponding $\cos\beta = \frac{c_a}{c}$ relationship are not enough to justify the $a^2 + b^2 = c^2$ relationship. That is why the teacher E. Gurbanova drew the students' attention to the possibility of finding $\cos\alpha$ and $\cos\beta$'s own triangle in the drawing using the other as well as the feasibility of doing so.

By the cognitive activity of the students, the proportions from $\triangle ABC$ $\cos\alpha = \frac{a}{c}$ and $\cos\beta = \frac{b}{c}$ are determined. From here, however, $\cos\alpha = \frac{c_b}{c} = \frac{b}{c}$ and $\cos\beta = \frac{c_a}{c} = \frac{a}{c}$. From here, $a^2 = c_a c$ and $b^2 = c_b c$. So, $a^2 + b^2 = c(c_a + c_b) = c^2$. Thus, it is determined that the sum of the squares of the lengths of the cathets of any rectangular tangent is equal to the square of the length of the hypotenuse.

The teacher directs children's $a^2 = c_a c$ attention to their attitude. It requires them to express this attitude in words. Students determine with cognitive activity that in a right-angled triangle, the leg is proportional to the hypotenuse and the adjacent part of the perpendicular drawn from the vertex of the right angle to the hypotenuse.

Let us present one more example. In the lesson organized and managed by Esmira Samadova, a math teacher of the Upper Leki settlement school of Agdash district, on the topic of "Solving a quadratic equation by dividing the square of a binomial", we observed that she preferred the analytical activity of students and in

this process, the methodical structure was in accordance with the general logic of mastering.

The teacher started the lesson by checking the results of the work given as homework. Tasks to be completed by students at home are listed below.

Task №1. The area of the square is 12 cm larger than the area of the circle. If the area of the circle is 36 cm^2 , find the side of the square.

Task №2. The area of a rectangle whose length is 4 cm greater than its width is equal to 60 cm^2 . Find the perimeter of the rectangle.

At the beginning of the homework checking process, the students tell the teacher that they do not know the solution to the second task and that they could not complete it. So, the equation they produced does not match the examples they were able to solve $ax^2 = 0$, $ax^2 + bx = 0$. The teacher confirms that the equation they obtained is a perfect quadratic equation $ax^2 + bx + c$ and explains that to solve it, you need to use the rule of subtracting the perfect square from the trinomial.

M.: You, dear students, have not made a mistake in your approach. You correctly accepted the width of the rectangle x sm according to the condition of the problem, then you accepted the area of the rectangle $(x + 4)sm$ based on the logic of the length $x(x + 4) = 60$ or $x^2 + 4x - 60 = 0$

Therefore, to solve the quadratic equation $x^2 + 4x - 60 = 0$, you can solve it by the method known to you, separating the full Square from the triad $x^2 + 4x - 60$. Continuing, the teacher brings to the attention of students that by adding and subtracting 4 to the triad $x^2 + 4x - 60$, it can be brought to the form $(x^2 + 4x + 4) - 4 - 60 = (x + 2)^2 - 64$. So, you need to solve

the equation $(x + 2)^2 - 64 = 0$ (and this is not difficult for students) ...

The teacher suggests that we learn how to solve the solution of equations in the form $ax^2 + bx + c = 0$ by separating the square of the quadrilateral from the quadrilateral, to determine the steps that we need to take for this. With the cognitive activity of students, the sequence of self-contained steps was determined below:

1. $ax^2 + bx + c = a(x^2 + \frac{b}{a}x + \frac{c}{a})$
2. $\frac{b}{a}x$ expression $2\frac{b}{2a}x$ ($\frac{b}{a}$ show in the form of two times the product of the number x) and reducing $a(x^2 + \frac{b}{a}x + \frac{c}{a})$ to $a(x^2 + 2\frac{b}{2a}x + \frac{c}{a})$
3. $\frac{b}{2a}$ - by adding $\frac{b^2}{4a^2}$ and subtracting the square of the number from $x^2 + 2\frac{b}{2a}x + \frac{c}{a}$ its expression $ax^2 + bx + c = a\left[\left(x^2 + 2\frac{b}{2a}x + \frac{b^2}{4a^2}\right) - \frac{b^2}{4a^2} + \frac{c}{a}\right]$ get the result;
4. $x^2 + 2\frac{b}{2a}x + \frac{b^2}{4a^2} = \left(x + \frac{b}{2a}\right)^2 \vee \frac{b^2}{4a^2} + \frac{c}{a} = -\frac{b^2 - 4ac}{4a^2}$ and performing the same conversions
 $ax^2 + bx + c = a\left[\left(x^2 + 2\frac{b}{2a}x + \frac{b^2}{4a^2}\right) - \frac{b^2}{4a^2} + \frac{c}{a}\right] = a\left(x + \frac{b}{2a}\right)^2 - \frac{b^2 - 4ac}{4a}$
 get the result.

The teacher once again notes that $ax^2 + bx + c = a\left(x + \frac{b}{2a}\right)^2 - \frac{b^2 - 4ac}{4a}$ its transformation is called the separation of a perfect square from a square trinomial.

Independent work 1. Separate the perfect square from $12x^2 + 7x + 1$ trinomials using the algorithm (The result is analyzed)

Independent work 2. Referring to the solution of $Ax^2 + B = 0$ $a\left(x + \frac{b}{2a}\right)^2 - \frac{b^2 - 4ac}{4a} = 0$ solve the equation.

It is noted that here and $Ax^2 = a\left(x + \frac{b}{2a}\right)^2 \vee B = -\frac{b^2 - 4ac}{4a}$

$$a\left(x + \frac{b}{2a}\right)^2 = -\frac{b^2 - 4ac}{4a}; \left(x + \frac{b}{2a}\right)^2 = \frac{b^2 - 4ac}{4a^2}$$

$$; x + \frac{b}{2a} = \pm \frac{\sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a} \quad x = \frac{b \pm \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a}$$

$$x_1 = \frac{b + \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a} \quad x_2 = \frac{b - \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a}$$

The task solving process is summarized. After the work (frontal) on solving the equations $x^2 + 8x - 1 = 0$ (the case with two roots), $x^2 + 4x + 10 = 0$ (the case with no real root), $3x^2 - 5x - 2 = 0$ (the case with two roots) based on the algorithm, the teacher informs the students that in order to separate the perfect square $ax^2 + bx + c = a\left(x + \frac{b}{2a}\right)^2 - \frac{b^2 - 4ac}{4a} = 0$ in the analytical writing of the dependence, the rule of writing the corresponding values of the parameters can be used.

M.: Who can do this job? (The vast majority of students say that they want to do this job.)

$x^2 - 8x + 36 = 0$ equation is solved.

As an independent study, four equations are proposed for options. 1. $x^2 + 9x + 14 = 0$;

$$2. x^2 + 3x - 10 = 0; 3. x^2 - 2x - 1 = 0; 4. x^2 - 4x + 3 = 0$$

The result is checked, appropriate notes are made.

M.: When solving equations, what do we want to achieve: do we want to solve the perfect square, or are we looking for the solution?

Sh.:... (Students say that the main task is to find the roots of the equation).

M.: So, why when you solve the equation $x_1 = \frac{b + \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a}$; $x_2 = \frac{b - \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a}$ not using formulas?

Note 1: During the analysis, the teacher said that I had achieved my wish, the students had learned the algorithm of dividing a complete square, and even its composition. That's why I found it necessary to ask such a question.

Note 2. Time does not allow students to solve equations using these formulas.

The teacher gives homework.

Solve the equations: 1) $12x^2 + 7x + 1 = 0$; 2) $x^2 - 12x + 36 = 0$; 3) $7x^2 - 25x + 23 = 0$

From the notes in the teacher's thematic plan, we learned that the teacher intends to continue the students' activities in the next lesson by involving them in the formulation of various forms of the quadratic equation solving algorithm in connection with the execution of tasks.

Scientific novelty of the research. 1) It has been pointed out that the efficiency of the management of the training process, which is a complete system, depends on finding the adequacy between its content and form; 2) The training process, which is considered as a way to implement education, which is considered necessary to be formed according to the calls of the IV industrial revolution, should be student-centered (student-centered); 3) In order to realize the requirement that the training process should be student-centered (student-centered), the optimal relations of analytical and heuristic activity of the student should be regulated in the said process along with a number of other conditions; 4) The existence of an environment for optimal regulation of analytical and heuristic activity in the training process depends on the logical connection of the substructures (external and internal structures) of its organizational form, the selection of the elements of each substructure and the level of the ability of these elements to realize their functions;

Practical significance of research. We believe that referring to the scientific innovations obtained in the research process will have a positive effect on the efficiency of the practical teacher's activity (activities on the organization and management of the educational process).

The result 1.1. There is a diversity of opinions in the interpretations (scientific interpretations) regarding the concept of organizational form of training, although the training practice has confirmed that the main organizational form of training in general education schools is the lesson; 1.2. Continuous improvement of the lesson as the main organizational form of education is an urgent and permanent problem; 2.1. The effectiveness of managing the learning process, which is a complete system, depends on finding the right balance between

its content and form; 2.2. The training process, understood as a way to implement education, which is considered necessary to be formed according to the calls of the IV industrial revolution, should be student-centered (student-centered); 2.3. In order to realize the requirement that the training process be student-centered (learner-centered), the optimal relations of the analytical and heuristic activity of the learner, along with a number of other conditions, should be regulated in the mentioned process.;3. The nature of the methodical substructure of the lesson does not depend only on the content of its general didactic structure, and the didactic structure reflects the main stages of training and the organization of a modern lesson; 4. The connecting links between the didactic and methodical structure serve the internal logical-psychological substructures of the lesson, and the internal substructure of the lesson consists of elements that reflect the teaching-cognitive process; 5. The regulation of the optimal relations of analytical and heuristic activity in the training process depends on the logical connection of substructures (external and internal structures) of its organizational form, the selection of elements of each substructure and the level of the ability of these elements to realize their functions; 6. Teachers with advanced experience comprehensively analyze the learning material for all components, as well as from the logical, psychological, educational and didactic aspects, and based on this, determine the ratio of analytical and heuristic types in the student's activity; the methodical structure of management is determined on this basis.

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